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MANAGING BRANDS: CHALLENGES AND STRATEGIES

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ABSTRACT

The battle for a share of the customer's wallet and cut throat competition for every bit of market space has resulted in search for a powerful weapon that delivers sustainable competitive differentiation. Here it is important to quote Philip Kotler about his perception on brands, "Branding is expensive and time consuming and it can make or break a product". But even then, today, branding is such a strong force that hardly anything goes unbranded. No one had thought that commodities like Rice, Salt and Aata would be branded.

Experience suggests that no product can really be a lasting success unless it also makes headway towards becoming a successful brand. There has been much debate on acknowledging the value of a brand's intangible assets in a company's balance sheet. Indian companies have been slow to recognize their importance. Brands are now a central feature of consumer marketing, they are important in building long term relationships with the consumer, irrespective of the type of market. Their importance is now also being recognised in other markets including service and industrial. Investing in a brand builds consumer confidence and loyalty and allows for brand stretching. It requires a consistent and long term strategy. Only a few brands have emerged as truly global.

The challenges facing brand managers have multiplied in recent times. Brands are often the most valuable assets for companies ranging from Unilever to Nokia. Yet, they can lose their value overnight if not managed carefully.

This paper highlights the challenges faced by brand managers in managing brands. The paper presents the strategies for managing and building brands. Brands in future would have to engage with the consumer in a much more robust manner, touching them in ways that are socially and psychologically meaningful. In more complex social environment, brand connect becomes even more critical. Consumer brands would, therefore, have to build a subliminal connects with the consumers.

KEYWORDS: Brand, Marketing Mix, Multi Branding, Umbrella Brand, Managing Brands.

INTRODUCTION

The battle for a share of the customer's wallet and cut throat competition for every bit of market space has resulted in search for a powerful weapon that delivers sustainable competitive differentiation. Here it is important to quote Philip Kotler about his perception on brands, "Branding is expensive and time consuming and it can make or break a product". But even then, today, branding is such a strong force that hardly anything goes unbranded. No one had thought that commodities like Rice, Salt and Aata would be branded. Today when we go to shop, we ask not just salt but Tata Salt or Captain Cook Salt etc. A recent study done by Samsika Marketing Consultancy showed that an average Indian consumers 44 brands per day – from your toothpaste and soap to tea/coffee and breakfast, to the newspaper you read, to the clothes you wear to work, right up to the time you hit the bed at night. This brand culture is not going through an evolution; it is going through a Brand Revolution. Brands have been around for many years, in fact, since probably the turn of the century and the concept of brand management was first introduced as long ago as the 1950s, but they have come to the fore particularly during the 1980s and 1990s. Branding has become a feature of marketing activity not only in the consumer goods and services sectors but in the non-consumer areas as well. Strong brands help a company to maintain market share in the face of a changing competitive environment and it has been shown that a strong market share is associated with above-average profits. Brands have become assets in their own right. In addition, they represent low-risk opportunities for the manufacturer or service provider and they also represent reduced risk for the consumer. A brand is the name, term, sign, symbol or design or a combination of them which is intended to identify the goods or services of one seller or group of sellers and to differentiate them from those of competitors. Brand name is that part of the brand that can be vocalized. A brand name may be, but need not be, a trade name. For instance, Coco Cola is a trade name that is also the brand name of the company's leading product. Brand mark is that part of brand that can be recognized but cannot be vocalized such as design or symbol or distinctive colouring or lettering. A brand mark is symbol, design or distinctive colouring or lettering that cannot be spoken.

CLASSIFICATION OF BRANDS

Brands are classified into following categories:

(I) INDIVIDUAL BRAND: They are the separate brands used for different items or product lines sold by the firm. Here each product has a unique brand name.

Godrej	Evita, Vigil, Ganga, Cinthol, Marvel, Glory
HLL	Pears, Lux, Rexona, Lifebuoy
ITC	Wills, Capstan, Gold Flake

(II) FAMILY BRAND: Here one name is used for two or more individual products. Family branding is most effective for specialized firms or those with specialized product lines.

Godrej	Refrigerator, Almirah, Soap, Hair Dye, Cosmetic
Tata	Trucks, Tea, Watches, Steel, Machinery, Cars
Bata	Shoes, Sleepers, Socks
Ponds	Talcum Powder, Soap, Cold Cream
Maggie	Noodles, Sauce, Jam, Pickle
L & T	Telecommunication Equipments, Switches, Change Over Switches, Control Gears
Vimal	Suitings, Shirtings, Accessories
Kissan	Squashes, Sauce, Jams Ketchup

(III) GENERIC BRAND: A brand name becomes generic when the buyer refers the type of product he wants by the producer’s brand name. For instance, Dalda, Colgate, Surf, Jeep. The brand name becoming generic is dangerous for the marketer. The owner of the brand who has spent money and time to popularize and promote the brand has to be cautious enough to educate buyers to buy only his brand and not the products of other brands under his brand name.

BRAND FUNCTIONS

Brands perform several functions in the marketplace, some for the buyers and others for the sellers.

Brands functions for the buyers are:

- Brands reduce the time for product search
- Brands make the choice of the product easier for the buyers
- Brands reduce the cost of product search for the buyers
- Brands add to the identity and status of the buyers – he drives a Mercedes
- Brands reduce the risk factors for the buyers, in terms of quality, quantity, guarantee, resale price, after sale service

Brands functions for the sellers are:

- Brands reduce the cost of sales as brands almost presale the products
- Brands reduce their advertising and promotion costs
- Brands help in increasing the firm's share value
- Brands help in improved market focus in the advertising media
- Brands help sell the entire product range under one name
- Brands provide an automatic product differentiation
- Brands reduce the cost of training of sales staff
- Brands sellers can charge premium or skimming prices
- Brands help in providing the promotional plans of a market
- Brands provide an entry barrier for firms planning to enter the market with the same product
- Brands help in making the advertising messages simple as the name itself conveys everything to the buyers

BRAND STRENGTHS

Brands become synonymous with products and at times with companies. While the company gets the benefits of increased sales, improved market share, it has to spend a lot on marketing expenses like advertising, promotion, personal selling and training of the salespersons of different channel members. Each brand management has to decide on the level to which they want their brand to improve its value. There is a list of brand names which have acquired the cult status.

S. No.	Brand	Details
1	Adidas	German athletic shoes and sneakers were used by the popular rap music group, the RUN-DMC. In 1980, Nike overtook Adidas as the top selling athletic shoes in the US.
2	Bata	The shoe company's brand has been shoe personification in India. Today, the name spells for sportswear, cardigans besides shoes.
3	Compaq	Has now become part of Hewlett Packard (HP) and yet the brand Compaq has stayed as a quality brand for computers, laptops.
4	Dunlop	Dunlop tyres are world famous with factories in several countries
5	Dabur	It has become a famous brand in India and overseas for ayurvedic medicines. The ancient form of medicines of the country has been revived by Dabur.
6	Escorts	Has become a big brand in India for motorcycles, tractors and telecom.
7	Frito Lays	Have become popular branded potato chips in India.
8	Firestone	Has pioneered the pneumatic tyre industry and therefore its brand Firestone has become synonymous with tyres.
9	Hamdard	Is a known brand for alternative unani and ayurvedic medicines
10	Intercontinental brand	It is known for tyres as also for hotel chains
11	Jaipan	This brand sells frying pans and other utensils.
12	Kellogg's	It is the word famous brand for breakfast food cereals
13	Levis	Levis jeans do not need any introduction in India especially amongst the youth of the country.
14	Mercedes	Mercedes cars are a class apart and the brand Mercedes needs no recommendation anywhere in the world. It is a known car full of technology, strength and luxury.
15	Nestles	Nestles chocolates and health drinks are household names.
16	Parker	These pens do not need any introduction in the world of writing.
17	Revlon	Revlon as a brand for cosmetics is world famous.
18	Santro	Santro cars from Hyundai have got good brand recognition in India.
19	Tata	Tata is a household brand in India as it covers a lot of products including cars.
20	Zenith	Zenith computers have been competing under their Zenith brand in India against heavy international competition.

BRAND BUILDERS

Over the years certain celebrities like Amitabh Bachchan, Shah Rukh Khan, Sachin Tendulkar, Mahendra Singh Dhoni have themselves become big brands. They are like the king Midas, who had the power of converting all he touched into gold. Companies vie with one another in signing the celebrities for endorsing their brands. Some celebrities even let their names be used as brands. Perfumes have been named after Elizabeth Taylor, Zenat Aman, actresses, one from Hollywood and the other from Bollywood. Recently Sanjeev Kapoor the famous chef has given his name as brand to an oven.

Mascot as brands is also used by various companies. Amul introduced a little girl to project its butter as “utterly butterly delicious”. After a gap of around 50 years, Amul has created a new character Amul cheese boy to give a new identity to the brand. Cheese boy features on cheese packs.

MARKETING MIX FACTORS AND BRANDS

The marketing manager can plan profitable sales using factors, known as Marketing Mix Factors. These are:

- **PRODUCT AND BRAND:** The products that get a brand name are easily recognised by the customers, unlike the generic products. For this reason alone, even the erstwhile generic products like sugar and salt have been given brand names by the sellers. Brand names help the seller in advertising the product as a distinguished product as opposed to the other run of the mill products.
- **PACKAGING AND BRAND:** brand name occupies a prominent place in today's package as it is brand that is packed from the shelf. Brand gives a focus to the package and makes it stand out.
- **PRICE AND BRAND:** A well accepted brand allows the seller to keep a higher price than the competitors as customers accept the high price, as they believe in the value of the product. Brand equity dictates the price in as much as when competitors bring in newer products at lower prices, a good brand does not react in haste. Only when competitive pressure becomes severe that sellers may look at their pricing.
- **TRANSPORTATION AND BRANDS:** transportation look to provide service to good brands, as they are sure of getting their bills paid in time. Besides association with known and accepted brands gives them market recognition as the brand name rubs off their name too.
- **DISTRIBUTION AND BRAND:** for an established brand it becomes easy to select the best distribution channels as the channel members are assured of good sales due to high brand equity. Companies can diversify geographically as the channel members of the new area would welcome the brand with open arms. Unknown or rejected brands find it difficult to set up proper marketing channels.

- **SALES PROMOTION AND BRANDS:** High brand equity products at most times, do not need sales promotion, as there is always a demand for them. However, in the competitive market even the well-known brands like Coke have to plan sales promotion on a continuous basis. Brand name helps in easy identification of the promoted product.
- **ADVERTISING AND BRANDS:** Brand names give the advertising efforts their full thrust, as it is the brand that the company wants to promote through advertising. Advertising efforts, therefore, revolve around the brands. Sellers take full advantage of brand equity by using the same brand for related products by having brand extensions. However, if the new product does not come up to the level of original product it could dilute the brand equity of the main product and companies have to keep a vigil on the same.
- **RETAIL SALES AND MERCHANDISING AND BRANDS:** brands sell in retail and add to the merchandising efforts of the sellers. Companies have been devising 'Point of Purchase' advertising and product displays keeping in mind the brand and its equity.
- **PERSONAL SELLING AND BRANDS:** Selling becomes easy when the brand is well known and accepted by the customers because the brand presales the product as the customers are already convinced about the value of the product.

CHALLENGES IN MANAGING BRANDS

The challenges facing brand managers have multiplied in recent times. Brands are often the most valuable assets for companies ranging from Unilever to Nokia. Yet, they can lose their value overnight if not managed carefully. The important challenges in managing and building brands are mentioned herein below:

- **BRAND IMAGE:** The first challenge in building a brand is to develop a brand image. The challenge is to connect the brand effectively with the customer.
- **LAUNCHING NEW BRANDS:** While the fundamental principles of brand management may not have changed much over the years, launching new brands has become trickier. In the past, building a brand was rather simple. It required little more than an occasional advertisement on a few television or radio stations highlighting the products superior features. Brands such as Coca-Cola, Kodak etc easily established themselves. Over time, brand building has become much trickier. As manufacturing standards have risen, it has become harder for firms to differentiate their products on quality alone.
- **BRAND DILUTION:** Brand managers have to face the challenge of brand dilution increasingly. This will happen as new brands emerge and customer no longer associates a brand with a particular class of product.
- **COMMUNICATION WITH CONSUMERS BECOMES HARDER:** Another challenge for marketers is that consumers have become harder to reach. They are busier;

more distracted and lead more complicated and less predictable lives. It is common to see husband and wife spending a lot of time outside home. Communicating with them and building a community of brand loyalists have become much more difficult.

- **UMBRELLA BRANDS:** Firms will need to strike a balance between having multiple brands in a product category versus building one powerful brand. Many companies will have to manage multiple brands and create umbrella brands which provide variety through the use of sub-brands.
- **CHALLENGE OF UNDERSTANDING THE EMOTIONAL NEEDS OF CUSTOMERS:** Yet another challenge with brand managing and building today is that in many cases customers pay a premium not because of its functionality but because it represents a way of life. Companies have to understand the emotional needs as well as the functional ones.
- **LOCALISATION VS. GLOBALISATION:** The brand managers are facing a challenge of localisation and globalisation. They should be very sensitive to the environment while taking decision about whether, when, where and how to globalise or localise the brand.
- **CHALLENGE FROM PROTESTERS:** Another factor which has made brand management more challenging is that brands give protesters far more power over companies than they would otherwise have. Coke and Pepsi faced a major backlash in India following media reports about pesticide contamination. Anti-globalisation supporters, environmentalists and NGOs can use the power of the brand against companies by mobilizing evidence of ill treated workers and polluted workers.
- **CULTURAL DISPARITIES:** A great deal of diversity exists in geographical markets in terms of physical conditions and marketing infrastructure, not to mention political and cultural issues which may have an impact at the brand and advertising level. Cultural disparities can be a major stumbling block for the generation of transnational brand names.

STRATEGIES IN MANAGING BRANDS

Some of the commonly branding strategies adopted by the companies are as follows:

- **USE OF CELEBRITY IN ADVERTISING:** Advertising circles have always maintained that celebrity endorsements, if used carefully, can help both the brand and the celebrity. The choice of the right celebrity is very crucial. He/she should have high recognition, high positive effect and high appropriateness to the product. Marketers have used celebrities since times immemorial to endorse the products. A well chosen celebrity can be successfully used to draw attention to the product.
- **REVITALIZING BRANDS:** A number of changes can occur in a market over time including changes in consumer tastes and preferences, emergence of new technology and competitors, a change in the regulatory environment. All these can adversely impact the

fortunes of a brand and a number of brands across categories have faded or virtually disappeared over the years. But a number of other brands have managed to stage successful comebacks in recent years through new marketing programmes and at times renewed consumer interest. Revitalizing a brand requires either that lost sources of brand equity are recaptured or new sources of brand equity are identified and established.

- **USE OF MULTI-BRANDING AS BRAND STRATEGY:** Multi brand strategy simultaneously works with more than one brand and reaps benefits from all of them. Companies often introduce additional brands in the same product category. Success depends on how quickly and instinctively a consumer can differentiate between the brands and yet recognise that they are from the same company. For instance, Kelvinator-Electrolux – Voltas and Allwyn
- **USE OF RELATIONSHIP MARKETING TO PREVENT BRAND SWITCHING:** The relationship marketing is the concept of life time value of a customer. It means that if a customer keeps buying the same product over his entire life time, it adds up to a tidy sum. It is interactive relationship where in customers' retention is very important as with increasing competition, it becomes extremely expensive to replace a new customer for an old one. Marketer has to know his customers thoroughly, tailor programmes according to their needs and communicate with them one by one.
- **USE OF SALES PROMOTION FOR BRAND BUILDING:** Win!!! Gifts!!! Prize!!! Or contests!! 30 % off!, buy one get one free! And 20 % more at no extra cost! All these are aimed at rewarding customers to reduce dissonance so that customer is rewarded for having made the decision to buy the product. Sales promotions are used cleverly to magnify the value of the brand continuously. It many companies launch similar sales promotions in terms of contest or prize, the one get gains most from the sales promotions is the one that does it first. Sales promotions are most effective when customers have a spontaneous desire to spend. So there should be proper focus on the timings.
- **INTEGRATING BRAND MANAGEMENT AND CORPORATE STRATEGY:** In today's business environment, the traditional approach to brand management needs a total reorientation. Brands must be viewed as strategic assets. Brand management must be integrated into corporate strategy. A strategic approach to brand management, among other things, calls for top management involvement, cross-functional approach, building trust and discharging social responsibility.
- **USE OF ONLINE PROMOTIONAL QUIZZES AND GAMES FOR BRAND BUILDING:** Marketers are always looking for that edge which would differentiate them from the customers, while still keeping a common goal in mind "entrap the customers". The biggest advantage of online promotional activities is that the net is an interactive medium. The ability to assimilate data is the biggest advantage that online promotions offer. When ever a customer registers on the site to enter a contest, he has to fill up a form containing a number of fields that include full address, sex, occupation, income,

interest and so on. . Total privacy could be assured, yet the firms could know of the styles, colour preferences helping to plan the product line better.

- **USE OF BRAND REPOSITIONING STRATEGY:** A shift in consumer preferences may leave the brand with less demand, compelling the company to reposition it. While there is cut throat competition, a competitor may launch a brand next to the company's brand and cut into its market share. However, well positioned a brand is in a market, the companies may have to reposition it later.
- **REINFORCING BRANDS:** Reinforcing brands involves ensuring innovation in product design, manufacturing and merchandising and ensuring relevance in user and usage imagery. Another critical consideration in reinforcing brands is the consistency of the marketing support that the brand receives. Both in terms of the amount and the nature of that support.
- **USE OF EVENT SPONSORSHIP AND ADVERTISING:** The cricket world cup and other tournaments present opportunity to reiterate the line between Pepsi and Cricket. Just as it does for Coca Cola. Just it does for Castrol. The fact of the matter is that every brand is trying to link itself with the game. But every brand is trying to the same, running the risk of dulling its differentiation. Companies sense an opportunity to use the heightened awareness about the events like World Cup for some associated selling. In events like 20-20 world cup India's population cutting across religion, region, race, is just the right audience for launching a brand. The kind of blitz that the advertising for a brand must create to earn top of mind attention quickly of the telecasts is well suited to the mass viewership of the telecast.
- **USE OF GLOBAL BRANDS:** Global branding is where there is an attempt to provide a common personality and positioning in every region of the world. This has been fuelled by improvements in communications and the growth in international travel. Standardization of the product in this way helps to contribute to economies of scale as does standardization of marketing activities.
- **ROLE OF ADVERTISING AGENCY IN MANAGING BRANDS:** The role of an ad agency in a brand's success story is a topic of much debate. While there's a school of thought that says that advertising is a peripheral component in the overall marketing mix--even though it draws a disproportionate share of attention---many others prescribe to the view that agencies play an integral role in managing brand as well as brand building. Yet, by and large, collective marketing wisdom is strongly in favour of advertising and its creators.

PRINCIPLES OF BRANDING

The important principles of a good brand name are:

- A brand name should suggest something about the product's characteristics, its benefits, use or action. For instance, EZZE implies easy to use, GOOD NIGHT, a mosquito repellent suggests that one can have a good sleep at night with it.
- It would be capable of being registered and legally protected.
- It should be distinctive, for instance, a name like 'chancellor' a cigarette brand name portrays, status, power and lavish like style.
- It should be easy to pronounce, spell and remember. It should be simple and short, for instance, VIMAL, ONIDA, COKE, etc.
- It should elicit a picture or image. Names that do this are "dual coded" in the sense that people remember them most because the name is stored in pictures and words.
- It should be meaningful. This is hard to do when a nonsense word is used. It can be overcome with lots of advertising, but names that are inherently more meaningful to customers are more readily stored in memory.

ET BRAND EQUITY'S ANNUAL SURVEY 2011

Colgate rapid progression to become the most trusted brand in Economic Times Brand Equity's annual survey is as much a statement of the brand's popular appeal as of India's FMCG success. ET's Most Trusted Brands survey seems to have thrown up other interesting trends too. No less remarkable is Tata Salt's climb to the 13 rank. It shows that even a commodity like salt can be successfully branded in a sustained manner. Rapid addition in mobile subscriber numbers, faster obsolescence and pervasive use has kept mobile handsets high on customer mindspace (Nokia on 4th Position, down from 1st last year). FMCG brands meanwhile, appear to have taken a lead. Colgate has topped the slot while ever popular Dettol continues to slide and is down from second slot in 2003 to number six now. FMCG brands traditionally did well in the study

TOP 100 BRANDS ACCORDING TO ET BRAND EQUITY'S ANNUAL SURVEY 2011

The table below depicts the top 100 brands as per Economic Times Brand Equity's Annual Survey, 2011.

Rank	Brand	Rank	Brand	Rank	Brand	Rank	Brand
1	Colgate	26	Surf	51	Rexona	76	Ariel
2	Lux	27	Samsung	52	Complan	77	Iodex
3	Airtel	28	Idea	53	Zandu Balm	78	Vaseline
4	Lifebuoy	29	Cinthol	54	Sprite	79	Nirma
5	Nokia	30	Kurkure	55	Sunfeast	80	Wheel
6	Dettol	31	Frooti	56	Vim	81	Perk
7	Britannia	32	Maaza	57	5 Star	82	Munch
8	Vodafone	33	LG	58	Fevicol	83	Godrej No. 1
9	Maggi	34	Pepsodent	59	Godrej	84	Philips
10	Close Up	35	Bata	60	Dove	85	Hajmola
11	Coca Cola	36	Tata Tea	61	Boost	86	Mortein
12	Fair & Lovely	37	Amul	62	Rasna	87	Medimix
13	Tata Salt	38	All Out	63	Sony	88	Honda (2 Wheelers)
14	Clinic Plus	39	Parle	64	Kit Kat	89	Amrutanjan Balm
15	Sunsilk	40	Johnson & Johnson	65	Tata Docomo	90	Videocon
16	Thums Up	41	SBI	66	Dabur	91	Garnier
17	Vicks	42	Big Bazar	67	Tata Indicom	92	Onida
18	Pond's	43	Hero Motocorp	68	Cadbury Eclairs	93	Eno
19	Mirinda	44	Santoor	69	Ujala	94	Centerfresh
20	Bournvita	45	Cadbury Dairy Milk	70	Aircel	95	Parachute
21	Pepsi	46	Moov	71	Samsung Mobile	96	LG Mobile
22	Head & Shoulders	47	Fanta	72	Limca	97	Babool
23	BSNL	48	Slice	73	Titan	98	Bajaj Motorcycles
24	Horlicks	49	Rin	74	Tide	99	Annapurna
25	7 UP	50	Goodknight	75	Pears	100	Pantene

TOP TEN BRANDS FROM 2001 – 2011

The top ten brands as per ET Brand Equity’s Annual Survey from 2001 to 2011 are mentioned herein below:

	2011	2010	2009	2008	2007	2006 *	2004	2003	2002	2001
1	Colgate	Nokia	Nokia	Nokia	Colgate	Colgate	Colgate	Colgate	Dettol	Lux
2	Lux	Colgate	Colgate	Colgate	Vicks	Lux	Lux	Dettol	Britannia	Colgate
3	Airtel	Lux	Lux	Tata Salt	Lux	Detto l	Rin	Pond’s	Colgate	Rin
4	Lifebuoy	Dettol	Lifebuoy	Pepso dent	Nokia	Pond’s	Detto l	Lux	Tata Salt	Thums Up
5	Nokia	Britannia	Dettol	Pond’s	Britannia	Tata Salt	Tata Salt	Pepso dent	Lux	Detto l
6	Dettol	Lifebuoy	Horlic ks	Lux	Dettol	LIC	Pond’s	Tata Salt	Coca Cola	Fair & Love ly
7	Britannia	Clinic Plus	Tata Salt	Britannia	Lifebuoy	Vicks	Fair & Lovel y	Britannia	Pepso dent	Surf
8	Vodaf one	Pond’s	Pepso dent	Dettol	Pepso dent	Brita nnia	Brita nnia	Rin	Pond’s	Coca Cola
9	Maggi	Fair & Lovel y	Britannia	Lifebuoy	Pond’s	Rin	Vicks	Surf	Pepsi	Pepsi
10	Close Up	Pepso dent	Relian ce Mobil e	Vicks	Tata Tea	Bata	Bata	Close Up	Thums Up	Horlic ks

* Combined Study of 2005 & 2006

POWER OF MOTHER BRAND OR MASTER BRAND

It’s an every day occurrence for salesmen all over India to reassure indecisive customers thus: ‘Don’t worry sir, yeh Tata ka product hai’ or Le leejiya behenji, Dabur company ka maal hai.’ In a majority of cases, these lines do the trick and the deal is struck. Such is the power of mother brands-----or master brands-----like Tata, Hero Honda, Dabur, Maruti, Bajaj and Godrej. The

names invariably serve as a hallmark of quality, reliability and leadership to consumers, and the transfer of trust onto products that bear one or the other of these names is relatively easy. A mother brand name clearly imparts confidence to consumers and creates comfort in buying a product. It creates instant recognition for the sub-brands.

While usually, sub-brands in the portfolio inherit the values of the mother brand, the opposite also holds true. Sometimes, it's a flagship brand that imbues values to the mother brand, which then gets passed on to other sub-brands. Splendor from Hero Honda is a case in point. Both brands complement each other. They synonymously stand for higher fuel efficiency, dependable, quality, great value. But it's the original fuel-sipper, Hero Honda CD 100 that first gave the mother brand the core value of 'fuel efficiency'. Similarly, it was the Maruti 800 that lent brand Maruti its values of 'value-for-money' and 'reliable family car'.

In fact, in the case of Bajaj Auto, its sub-brands have played a huge role in changing the image of the mother brand. Once associated positively with reliable, value-for-money scooter, the mother brand's image took a downturn when its clunky scooters began losing the race to the consumer's new fancy – motorcycles. And even though Baja Auto had a portfolio of motorcycles, the abiding 'Bajaj image' was that of the fuddy-duddy scooters. At the turn of the millennium, the company launched its performance bike, Pulsar, which was well received. Then came motorcycle brands like Bajaj Platina and Bajaj Discover, which not only worked in the market, but also re-emphasized Baja Auto's connection with bikes, it used the sub-brands to change the positioning of the mother brand from 'value-for-money' to 'aspirational' to 'distinctly ahead'.

MANAGING BRANDS – CASE STUDIES OF SELECTED PRODUCTS/ COMPANIES

- **COLGATE:** In the last four quarters, Colgate has been aggressive with the launch of Colgate Active Salt and Colgate MaxFresh to widen the gap between itself and the competition. The rural market has been one of the main thrust areas for Colgate—for instance, initiatives like project Jagruti and recently Project Disha have been undertaken. Project Disha is aimed at establishing Colgate as a brand against look-alikes and regional players.
- **LIFE INSURANCE CORPORATION OF INDIA:** While many legacy brands appear to be suffering from the wear and tear of time, LIC has clearly leveraged its vast reservoir of experience in the insurance business, focusing on attributes—like customer centricity, efficient service and quick response—that have added to the brand's trust. LIC has built its image on trust. It is not surprising that the public sector insurer has retained dominant market share in the life insurance category, despite the entry of several private players over the last decade. The company has introduced several initiatives to improve its offerings in the last five years. For instance, it has introduced a facilitated settlement of survival benefits without calling for policy documents, concessions to customers for reviving their lapsed policies, and alternate channels for payment of premium through ATMs, ECS, the internet and even SMS.

- **NOKIA:** Nokia was very consistent in its marketing and communication. Unlike marketing paradigms where brands are slotted ‘premium’ or ‘popular’ based on the price point, Nokia consistently pitched itself as an ‘aspirational brand’, regardless of the price point it played in. We could buy a Nokia at Rs. 35,000 or Rs. 3000 – it would still be aspirational. That consistency and commitment created a very strong emotional connect with the consumer and built trust. That’s why Nokia grew to become a 75 percent market share leader.
- **STATE BANK OF INDIA:** Until a few years ago, it was felt that SBI was a typical public sector bank, slow at embracing technology and lacking the ‘aggressiveness and refinement’ of some of the more high-profile private banks. But the bank has quietly transformed itself into a significant force on the back of initiatives like moving away from branch banking to core banking (which enables its customers to access the bank’s services and conduct transactions from any of its member branches). New technology will also help the bank capitalize on its distribution strength better. What is also working in SBI’s favour is the greater number of branches and ATMs it has compared to any other bank in India-its 10,000 plus branches outnumber the under – 1,000 branches of rivals like ICICI Bank and HDFC Bank.
- **SONATA WATCHES:** The Tata parentage has helped the brand to establish trust and reliability in a mass market otherwise populated by a host of local and unorganized players. The brand’s association with cricketer M. S. Dhoni has worked favourably as well. The spirit of confidence and achievement that Dhoni symbolizes fits well with the positioning of Sonata – a robust, confident brand for today’s progressive Indian youth.
- **TATA AIG LIFE INSURANCE COMPANY:** It combines the strength and integrity of the Tata Group with the international expertise and financial strength of the member companies of AIG Inc-the leading US based international insurance and financial services organisation. Having established the same, the new corporate identity – A new look at life – is the next logical step forward to the endorsement of the fact that it is walking the talk of its commitment and will continue to offer path-breaking products to its customers. To support its new identity the company is launching a multimedia brand campaign across television, press, outdoor, cinema and the internet.
- **TVS SCOOTY:** Since its launch in 1993, Scooty is the only automobile brand targeted at women. Women are very different from men in terms of self-expression, and for them convenience is more important than performance.

CONCLUSION

The job has never been so difficult! Today, markets are highly fragmented, competition is fierce, shelves are crowded, and private labels are stronger. On top of this, growth is limited, budgets are reduced, and short-term promotions are often the only weapon considered to grow a brand. In these conditions, launching a new product or a line extension, or managing or restaging an existing brand, is riskier than ever before.

Brands are now a central feature of consumer marketing, they are important in building long term relationships with the consumer, irrespective of the type of market. Their importance is now also being recognised in other markets including service and industrial. Investing in a brand builds consumer confidence and loyalty and allows for brand stretching. It requires a consistent and long term strategy. Only a few brands have emerged as truly global.

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